

RQs

RQ1: Performance Issues

RQ2: Performance Causes

Data Collection

Search Terms

"Performance Issues"
"Android Apps"

Q&A Posts

Stack Overflow

6059 Posts

Total Posts Reterived

385 Posts

Random Sampling

Data Extraction & Synthesis

Data Extraction

- Index
- Title
- Link
- Issue
- Cause

Synthesis

- Data Familiarization
- Initial Codes
- Issues & Causes Search
- Issues & Causes Review
- Categories